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Research Article

**PREDICTION OF THE EMOTIONAL DIVORCE ACCORDING
TO SPIRITUAL WELL-BEING AND SOCIAL SKILLS IN THE
COUPLES**Zahra Arayesh Kashkoli¹, Dr.Behnaz Baghbanbashi^{2*}¹Department of Psychology, Arsanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Arsanjan Iran²Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Arsanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University,
Arsanjan Iran**Abstract:**

Emotional divorce is one of the most important problems in life and an effective factor in the breakdown of the structure of the most fundamental part of society, namely the family. Due to the importance and position of the family system and its functions in the individual and social life of humans, it is very important to examine the affecting factors on it. Therefore, the present study aimed to investigate and predict the emotional divorce based on the variables of social skills and spiritual well-being of couples using the Metuchen social skills questionnaire (1983), Gatman's emotional divorce (1995), and spiritual well-being, Paloutzian and Ellison (1982) among 156 couples (312 males and females) by available sampling method. For data analysis, Pearson correlation coefficient and multivariate regression were used. At the end, the results of multiple regression analysis showed that considering the amount of significant level (Sig = 0,000), the spiritual well-being and social skills with 95% confidence can predict the divorce of the couple. The results also showed that there is a significant negative relationship between emotional divorce and spiritual well-being in couples. Similarly, there is a significant negative relationship between emotional divorce and couples' well-being. In addition, there was a significant relationship between age difference of couples, number of children, level of education of couples with emotional divorce at 95% level, but there was no significant statistical relationship between marriage and emotional divorce. In general, a variety of factors affective on the quality of marital life and decrease or increase the phenomenon of emotional divorce. According to the results, it can be stated that spiritual well-being and social skills play an important role in the prediction of emotional divorce.

Key words: emotional divorce, social skills. Spiritual well-being, Religious welfare**Corresponding author:****Dr.Behnaz Baghbanbashi**

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INTRODUCTION:

Family as the most important social institution in human societies is an appropriate environment for meeting the needs of family members and a suitable platform for the development of healthy, efficient, and generous generations to provide basic human needs and thus the foundation of community building. However, evidence suggests that in recent years, this important institution faces numerous challenges and challenges due to cultural, social, industrial, scientific and value developments. Meanwhile, one of the most important damages that seriously threatened this important institution. Divorce, in particular, is an emotional divorce. Experts believe that the process of divorce in most cases runs this way: minor differences, the repetition of minor differences and their seriousness, the separation or ending of one of the couples to the other, long and repeated rebellion, the fatigue of the couples from Limitations and conflicts are divorce and legal divorce. In general, emotional divorce is another type of divorce and a very important phenomenon that is not recorded anywhere. This type of divorce relates to families who decide for reasons such as family-based traditions or incorrect beliefs and negative attitudes toward divorced women, fear and concern for loneliness, loss of children or disability in meeting the needs of life, their wife lives under a roof. Since divorce is one of the most important factors in the disintegration of the most important social institution and the basis of society, namely, the family, divorce examination and especially the factors that lead to it are necessary in their own right. Also, the study of factors that tend to divorce couples is more important because of the consequences that follow. Therefore, the importance of the issue of divorce, considering the consequences and damage, can be raised; divorce damages can be as addiction, delinquency, crime and suicide, and so on. On the other hand, according to evidence in recent years, the number of divorce statistics has increased more than other times and consequently the number of crime crimes has also increased. Therefore, the study of effective factors such as spiritual well-being and social skills is of great importance. Therefore, the present study aims to predict emotional divorce with respect to the components of spiritual well-being and social skills.

Importance and necessity

In general, one of the most important issues in human life is divorce, especially emotional divorce. Because this phenomenon is targeted at the most basic social entity of human life, which will not result in a reduction of family and community functions, increase of mental and psychological pressures in the

community, therefore, to study this issue from the point of view A variety of scientific disciplines, including psychology and social medicine, are essential. Because the family is one of the most important of the first public and global institutional systems that are necessary for solving the vital and emotional needs of a person and the survival of society [1]. On the other hand, proper relationships in the society are formed based on the proper relationships in the family, and as much as the relationships within the family are more appropriate, the family and, consequently, the society have more stability and strength [2]. This shows the permanent presence of this social institution and its existential necessity. Principally, marriage is the basis for the formation of the family and the opposite is the divorce, which causes it to disappear [3]. Divorce has an individual, family and social collapse and has a more negative effect on women than men. Therefore, one of the most important family injuries is divorce, but the official statistics of divorce do not fully reflect the failure rate of spouses in marital life, because along with that larger statistic is devoted to emotional divorces, that is, they live together. But they do not demand legal divorce [4]. Indeed, some marriages do not end in divorce, they become marriages that are lacking in love, friendship, and friendship, and spouses move forward only with family life and spend time [5]. Therefore, the study of the issue of emotional divorce is of particular importance. Therefore, the present study examines the anticipation of emotional divorce based on the components of spiritual well-being and social skills of couples, due to the lack of study in this regard, since conducting such research to examine the status of emotional divorce in society, problems and The consequences of the awareness of the people and authorities of different societies are necessary to deal with it. Also, in the presence of the relationship and meaningfulness of the results, awareness raising and education can be considered as an important step in reducing emotional divorce and improving couples' relationships in society.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This research has been applied in a targeted and applied way and has been survey based on data collection method. Descriptive research is a correlation study.

Statistical population, statistical sample and sampling method

The population of this study is all married couples (male and female) in Shiraz with children with knowledgeable children. To this end, 156 couples (312 males and females) were selected using available sampling. The explanation is that in this

study, referring to the Education Department of Shiraz and obtaining a license from it, referring to 5 schools in different parts of Shiraz, 312

questionnaires were distributed among the students of the districts And it's explained how to fill in and who to fill.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondents based on the duration of marriage

Descriptive Statistics			Time period (year)	Variable
Valid percentage	Percent	Abundance		
9.6	9.6	30	10-5	Duration of marriage
89.1	79.5	248	20-11	
96.8	7.7	24	30-21	
100	3.2	11	More than 30 years	
100	100	312		

Research tools

In general, a tool for collecting information in this study is a questionnaire that is presented below:

1 Matson Social Skills Questionnaire (1983)

To measure social skills of couples in this study, a social skills measurement scale was developed by Matsson et al. (1983).

2 Gottman's Ethical Divorce Scale (1995)

The purpose of this research is to measure the emotional divorce of a questionnaire made by Guttman (1995).

3 Spiritual well-being questionnaires

The original version of this questionnaire was prepared by Palutozian and Ellison in the year 1982, and this questionnaire has 20 items.

Research methodology

To collect information in this study, Gatman's emotional divorce questionnaire, Matson's Social Skills Questionnaire (1983), and Paltzian and Ellison Welfare Questionnaire were used. To this end, questionnaires were given to school students by introducing the university and obtaining permission from their respective schools. The subjects were sampled and completed all three questionnaires together. To motivate the couples before studying the questionnaire, the research goals and its significance were explained.

Statistical analysis of data

Descriptive statistical methods (frequency, mean, standard deviation of maximum and minimum), and inferential (Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression) were used based on research type.

Table 2: Descriptive indices of research variables

	At least	Maximum	Average		Standard deviation	Number
			Average	Mistake criterion		
Emotional Divorce	30	59	48.68	0.92	7.18	312
Spiritual well-being	57	115	92	2.036	15.77	312
Religious welfare	30	60	50.5	1.1	8.53	312
Existential well-being	23	55	41.5	1.1	8.54	312
social skills	117	206	154.15	2.53	19.61	312

Table 3: Results of a Normality Test

		Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
		statistics	Degrees of freedom	significance level	statistics	Degrees of freedom	significance level
dimensions of spiritual well-being	Religious welfare	168	312	0.0001	0.890	312	0.0001
	Existential well-being	0.107	312	0.087	0.953	312	0.061
Spiritual well-being		0.141	312	0.4	921	312	0.1
Emotional Divorce		0.134	312	0.09	0.938	312	0.04
social skills		0.087	312	0.200	0.969	312	0.129

First hypothesis

1- The components of spiritual well-being and social skills of individuals are able to predict the emotional divorce of couples.

Table 4: Correlation matrix of emotional divorce and spiritual well-being couples and social skills of couples using Pearson correlation test at 95% significance level

		Emotional Divorce	Spiritual well-being	Religious welfare	Existential well-being	
Emotional Divorce	correlation coefficient	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	312				
Spiritual well-being	correlation coefficient	-0.101	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.041				
	N	312	312			
Religious welfare	correlation coefficient	0.1	0.623**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.449	0.000			
	N	312	312	312		
Existential well-being	correlation coefficient	0.087	0.923**	0.705**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.007	0.000	0.000		
	N	312	312	312	312	
social skills	correlation coefficient	-0.420	0.515**	0.361**	0.271**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	0.021	0.010	0.040	
	N	312	312	312	312	312

Table 5: Results of standard and non-standard regression coefficients for predicting couples' emotional divorce

Multi-line statistics		Meaningful	T	Standard coefficients	Non-standard coefficients		Model
VIF	Tolerance			Beta	standard error	B	
-	-	0.016	2.488		8.46	21.063	Fixed
1.021	0.979	0.001	3.498	0.426	0.045	0.156	social skills
1.77	0.56	0.017	-1.63	-0.210	1.34	2.21	Spiritual well-being
2.027	0.493	0.007	-0.041	-0.007	0.143	-0.006	Religious welfare
2.022	0.495	0.018	0.651	0.111	0.144	0.094	Existential well-being

Table 6: Analysis of variance of regression

Model	sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	average of squares	F	Sig.
regression	572.19	3	190.73	36.185	0.008
Remaining	2472.793	308	157		
Total	3055.98	301			

The second hypothesis

2. There is a significant relationship between emotional divorce and couples' social skills.

Table 7: Results of the study of the relationship between emotional divorce and couples' social skills using Pearson correlation test at 95% significance level

		Emotional Divorce	social skills
Emotional Divorce	Pearson	1	-0.420
	Sig.	-	0.001
	Number	312	312
social skills	Pearson	-0.420	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	Number	312	312

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Hypothesis 1, the components of spiritual well-being and social skills of individuals are able to predict the emotional divorce of couples.

In order to investigate and anticipate the divorce using spiritual well-being and social skills, multiple regression methods were used simultaneously or standardized. In general, the results of analysis of variance showed a regression relation, considering the level of significance (Sig = 0.008), spiritual well-being and social skills with 95% confidence can predict couples' emotional divorce. The findings also showed that the variables entered in the regression analysis, have managed 71.3% of the variation of the dependent variable this means explaining the emotional divorce of couples. Considering the significance of the F value, it is also clear that the linear combination of independent variables in a meaningful way can explain and predict changes in the dependent variable (emotional divorce). Also, according to the beta column (standardized regression coefficients), the social skills variable has a higher beta value (Beta = 0.426, Sig = 0.001), more contribution to the definition of the criterion variable (directly) and then spiritual well-being (beta=0.210, Sig = 0.017), respectively. These results are consistent with the findings of Fuji and Naderi (2016), Narimani et al. (2014) and Seraji et al. (2016). Effective social skills will boost individuals and improve relationships and quality of life in individuals. This is while ineffective social skills prevent the growth of human beings, and for the relations of the verdict of the poison and even

destroys the relations. On the other hand, evidence suggests that social skills alone will not lead to a stable marital life. Because someone may have social skills, it's hard to get into other effective predictors of emotional divorce. Each of these predictive variables of emotional divorce can contribute to the emotional failure of couples in marital life, and the mere enjoyment of social skills cannot guarantee success in common life and the stability of marriage. Basically, life skills such as social skills are a behavior-based approach that by balancing knowledge, attitude and skill, can increase the skills of coping with stress and increase self-esteem and control the individual in different situations such as marital conflicts and increase divorce (Raisay et al., 2012). Also, according to existing evidence, one of the important aspects of control is the timing of social behaviors, or, in other words, their suitability to the existing situation. Because the signs of social inadequacy are timeless expressions (Harji, 1994). In explaining the relationship between the predictive value of spiritual well-being and emotional divorce, we can say that. That people with religious welfare have a more positive mental health and these people have a higher mental health. Individuals with stronger spiritual beliefs and well-being have better compatibility with stressful situations. And experience lower levels of negative emotions and have higher social support, which will increase couples' relationships in common, life and reduce emotional divorce in people with religious well-being. On the other hand, according to similar studies, people with higher levels of existential well-being experience a high level of

negative emotions. This may partially reduce couples' relationships and, consequently, increase emotional divorce (Narimani et al., 2014, Fuji and Naderi, 2015).

The second hypothesis, there is a significant relationship between emotional divorce and social skills of couples.

The results of the study on the relationship between emotional divorce and social skills of couples, using Pearson correlation test, showed a significant negative relationship between emotional divorce and social skills in couples (Sig = 0.100). It means that the level of social skills of couples decreases in emotional divorce. These results are incompatible with the findings of Fuji and Naderi (2015). Concerning this issue, it can be argued that although social skills in the creation and maintenance of interpersonal relationships and the enhancement of pleasurable interactions have an undeniable effect, social skills can in some way affect couples' mutual relationships, and the reverse effect and have a detrimental effect on their relationships (Fuji and Naderi, 2015). Similarly, couples' disagreement with social skills can be another reason for explaining these outcomes. Barseland Denton (1992), with emphasis on the role of social skills in maintaining interpersonal interest and attraction by presenting a model of "similarities in social and cognitive-social skills", predicts similarities by reinforcing interactions. Enjoying gravity increases, and in spite of the discrepancy between couples, it can be harmful to strengthen these enjoyable interactions and thus improve the quality of life and marital life relationships.

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